

SCAN to BIM for Bridges: Extraction of Geometric Properties for Engineering Analysis

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Abstract

The automatic generation of the BIM model of a bridge from point clouds is important for accurate monitoring and management of the structure. The integration of BIM with point cloud data offers a powerful method for capturing and analyzing the geometric properties of civil infrastructure, particularly bridges. This thesis explores the process of creating a BIM model from point cloud data, specifically focusing on the geometric representation of a bridge. Using appropriate tools, point cloud data obtained from 3D laser scanner was processed to generate a detailed 3D model. The methodology involves converting the raw data into a structured BIM format, enabling the extraction of precise geometric properties necessary for maintenance, engineering analysis, and optimization.

The results demonstrate the accuracy and efficiency of point cloud-to-BIM conversion, emphasizing its potential to enhance bridge design, inspection, monitoring and lifecycle management. Challenges such as data density, noise, and the complexity of bridge components were addressed, leading to a refined approach that ensures a high degree of geometric fidelity. The

findings highlight the practical benefits of this integration, providing a foundation for future developments in automated infrastructure modeling. This work underscores the significance of point cloud-based BIM in bridge engineering and suggests areas for further research to improve the process and expand its applications.

Dissertation:

Link for full text

Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/rfaYnemB798>

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